

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE TOPIC OF "STOMACH AND INTESTINAL DISEASES"

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Abstract: This article presents comments on the didactic possibilities of electronic educational resources and interactive methods in increasing the effectiveness of teaching the topic "Stomach and intestinal diseases".

Keywords: Electronic education resource, interactive methods, pedagogical tool, pedagogical technology, innovative technology, "Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Continue", "Presentation", individualization.

Today, the formation of new social relations in our society, the integration of education into the world education system requires a new approach to modern pedagogical technologies. These approaches, in turn, bring certain positive changes to the organizational and methodological aspects of the educational process, many of which are inextricably linked with pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. It depends on the skill of the teacher to pass each lesson based on its own method, to increase the student's interest in science, and to awaken love for science in his heart. Modern pedagogical technologies are one of the tools that serve to improve the teacher's skills.

Modern pedagogical technology is a product of the development of modern didactics and pedagogy. Every modern pedagogue will surely achieve a positive result if he uses the existing pedagogical technologies in his lessons. The goal of today's teacher is to educate well-rounded young people, give them thorough education, provide them with the necessary information, teach them to think independently, create knowledge and life skills, instill in them the feelings of patriotism and patriotism. consists of finding These noble goals can be realized in training based on advanced pedagogical and innovative technologies.

Innovative technology - methods of improving knowledge acquisition through the use of factors that increase the effectiveness of education, the design and implementation of various pedagogical processes. Its main goal is to introduce innovations and changes in the activities of the teacher and learner in the educational process, which requires the use of interactive methods. Interactive methods are based on the activity of each learner participating in the educational process, free and independent thinking. Learning becomes an interesting activity

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when using these methods. For many years, traditional classes have been one of the main forms of education. In a traditional lesson, the teacher becomes an active participant, and the student becomes a passive participant. This prevents the development of the student's independent thinking and ability to search. At a time when information and communication technologies are rapidly developing, such lessons are not effective. Today's demand requires meaningful organization of the lesson process in an unconventional way, increasing students' interest and ensuring their activity in the educational process. The meaningful course of the lesson, the methods used in it and the results achieved determine the teacher's skill and level of knowledge.

If the methods are chosen correctly in the lesson, the goal will be achieved quickly and easily. The choice of interactive methods is based on the didactic purpose of each lesson. This requires the teacher to teach based on methods appropriate to the subject of the lesson, not always in the same way.

It is known that today there are more than a hundred types of interactive methods, most of which have been tested and have given good results. Effective results can be achieved in the lesson by using the widely used methods - "Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Continue", "Presentation", "Blitz survey", "Problem situation". "Sinquain", "Reverse test", "Wheel of Mind" methods are used in the part of the lesson to ask about the passed topic, "Insert", "Pinboard", "Zinama-zina", "Boomerang" technologies in the part of explaining the new topic, in the part of strengthening the topic Graphic organizers such as Venn Diagram, Fishbone, Why?, How?, Concept Chart, Lily Flower, and Concept Analysis, T-Table, Resume, The use of "Sunflower", "Charkhpalak" methods, "FSMU", "Cluster", "BBXB" methods for homework help to ensure the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the knowledge of students. Therefore, it is one of the urgent issues to further improve the methods of using interactive methods to effectively organize education and develop competence in the teaching of the topic "Stomach and intestinal diseases" in the human anatomy textbook. The use of multimedia presentations in anatomy classes makes it possible to create an educational process based on psychologically correct methods of attention, memory, mental activity, humanization of educational content and pedagogical interactions, restructuring of the educational process.

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In connection with the use of interactive methods in the training of the topic "Stomach and intestinal diseases", increasing the importance of providing educational information to students, the possibility of using different methods and forms of teaching, to ensure the visibility of any educational information learned by them, to use methods of learning, differentiation and individualization based on the modern methods of teaching independent methods, to ensure the successful learning of all categories of students provides This makes it possible to bring education in the science of human anatomy to a new level.

In short, to improve the quality of training of students in schools, it is necessary to improve the mechanism of comprehensive use of interactive electronic educational resources together with innovative forms and methods of teaching. It is important to use interactive e-learning resources to improve the effectiveness of teaching professional subjects, especially human anatomy.

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